

VOLLEYBALL GAME TECHNIQUE AND ITS RULES

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Annotation: this article also provides feedback on the types of volleyball game and their formation into the body. This also mainly deals with what the technique of the game of volleyball consists of.

Keywords: attack technique, defense technique, technique, types of ball transfer, area.

The game of volleyball consists of offensive and defensive techniques. The offense also has the likes of chess standing and sliding, passing and receiving the ball, scoring and returning the ball for one or two, blocking the path of the ball. The player's shay stands and slides. During a volleyball game, the player is in a ditch across the field and is sliding. The purpose of the shift is to choose a suitable place to receive the ball and implement other methods.

It is the player's constant willingness to slide for the most important point in standing in a sporting position. In a standing posture, the player will have their legs bent, the legs opened shoulder-width apart, one leg slightly forward, and the body also slightly forward. The hands should be bent at the elbow and the palms facing each other. This condition is not permanent, Of course it varies depending on the game's progress. If it is necessary to take a returning head from the round, the gamekeeper will bend much, straighten up when shooting.

A volleyball player can walk along the field with his legs swung (left, on it, forward, back), two steps (back and forth), jumping (running and steaming) (moving quickly across the field and changing direction at once). The last run step will be long, since after it it is possible to tuck, jump, change direction.

Pass the ball. This is a method of cross-passing the ball transmitted to the partner or opponent's side to continue the game. There are also ways to move the ball forward, up and back.

Depending on the flight trajectory of the Bush, short stretches of the long arm over the entire field are also applied to the field and extremely short ones to its own field. The ball is divided into low (1 meter above the net), Medium (up to 2 meters), and higher (over 2 meters), close (less than 0.5 meters) and longer (more than 0.5 meters), depending on the transmission height.

Transfer the ball from above with two supports. This is a very common method. With confidence and accuracy in this, the disposition is his side.

In the first instance, the player bends his legs at the knee and puts his hands forward with the palms slightly inward, the paws are held tense.

When the ball approaches, the legs are straightened and the torso is raised. The hands are squashed and the ball is prepared for reception. Hand posture and leg movements are coordinated. This makes it possible to get the ball to the appropriate place.

There is another type of transmission in which the ball is transmitted from two supports above, one support above, two supports above. But these methods are less used in the game. Nevertheless, it is necessary that each volleyball player quickly and accurately passes the ball and beats the shot in his direction.

Receiving the ball. It is a defensive technique in keeping the ball in play after an attack by opponents. Receiving the ball from the bottom with two supports is the main method in modern volleyball. He is the main method in the moment of a strong blow during an attack. In this method, the hands with the torso up or slightly bent are lowered forward, with one palm attached to the other. The ball is taken on the wrists. In order to soften the on the wrists, the hands are raised and bent closer to the elbow, the legs are straightened and the torso is raised. Receiving the ball from above with two supports. This method is adopted when the ball is coming less strongly, as well as when it is convenient to use another method.

Receiving the ball from the bottom in a support. This is also used because the accuracy of the method is sufficient, but it is useful when the ball is away from the game and there is an opportunity to apply another method, and another method is used. Straightened hand tense compressed paws block the path of the ball (hit the ball with a fist as well as palms or wrists). The foot does not participate in these activities.

Increase the ball. The introduction of the ball into the game is called an increase. Favorable for percussion are the key features of raising the pitch as well as striking the ball by shaking the hand, increasing the movement of the post-learning player. In increasing the ball can be fought with a fist or palm. In this, the ball is fired with one hand upwards. The direction and height of the upward throw depends on the method of execution. If the ball is kicked over the head it is called to increase from the bottom if it is rolled from the top to the bottom, and if it stands with the side it is called to increase the ball to the side.

Accordingly, there are four different methods of lifting: from bottom to bottom, from bottom to side, from top to right, from top to side.

Increase the ball from the bottom to the right. For a beginner in the game, this is the main method. He does it while looking in the direction of the species. The player holds the bush with a bent hand from the elbow. The other hand is stretched back to give the head a shot. After that, the paws are slightly bent, the ball is thrown 20-30 cm high up and hammered.

When the player strikes, they straighten their backward leg and enter the body weight on the foot ahead. After the shot, the player takes a the case in which we are, who is trying to ruin area.

Direct customer zarbi. It consists of hitting the ball at the top of the net towards the opponent with one support, this is called a feisty shot. This ingenious tattoo is performed by jumping up or coming to run. The cellist performs this tattoo by pressing one two and three steps. The player waits for the flying ball with the hands forward upwards, with the kicking hand being prepared for the shot. The body bi slightly bends back. The paws are held in a fist and bent towards the ground, then a kick is made, after which the foot falls along with the down ball. The stronger the ball War is needed, the looser the palm, the more tense the palm is.

Volleyball belongs to the team game type, and in the game two teams are obliged to play an elite person in each. The number of players in reserve can range from 2 to 6.

The players ' Sportswear is a T-shirt, shorts and slippers. Depending on the gender of the player's age, the height of the net will be as it is:

- Girls 13-14 years old-2m 10cm.

- 15-16 years old-2m 20cm.
- For women aged 17-18 years and older – 2m 24cm.
- Boys 15-16 years old - 2m 35cm.
- Men 17-18 years old or more-2m 43cm.

The game consists of three or five parties, with each party lasting up to 25 points. If the game points are 25-25, the game will last up to 27 points. At the last party, 3 or 5 game accounts are conducted on the basis of a “stick break”. That is, it is possible to bring a loss or a win to a team, regardless of which team has the right to enter each action in the game. In the deciding party, up to 15 points are played and continue until the difference of two points. In modern volleyball, a break of 1 minute is given after every 8 points, that is, a break is given when the score breaks to 8 and goes to 16. And in the last party, when there are 8 points, players exchange fields.

The first official rules of the game of volleyball was the 1997 American doctor A. Holsted under the direction of Produced. Some of the provisions of these provisions are made up of those under certain abands.

- Area size-7.6 × 16.1 m.
- Net height - 198 cm.
- The weight of the ball is 340 grm.

The ball was entered into the game standing on one foot in a 1×1 meter rectangular spot located on the right outside.

In addition to the fact that volleyball became increasingly popular and the participants went to form a game adventure, the rules of the competition were also changing.

- 1900 – the figure is up to 21 points, the height of the net is 213 cm.
- 1912-field 10,6x18, 2 mt, tour – 228sm.
- 1917 – score-15 points, round 243cm.
- 1918-number of players 6 in one team.
- 1922-playing the ball fakat 3 times, field 9, 1x18, 2 mt.
- 1925-ball 66-69sm, weight 275-285 gr, pitch 9x18 mt.

Volleyball is one of the most popular sports in all educational institutions of the Republic.

In modern volleyball, performing an effective game and achieving high results is carried out only at the cost of Super-Formed physical training. The special physical qualities that ensure the play effect of volleyball players are determined by two factors at all stages during the preparatory period: fast-strength training and a mixed factor of preparation.

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